

Kristien Hens: The Ethics of Comprehensive Chromosome Screening

On the 1st of April, Kristien Hens, Research Professor at the University of Antwerp and PI of the gender analysis part of B2-Inf held a lecture at the ESHRE campus course on Genetic counselling in preimplantation genetic testing (PGT), a course that took place from 31st of March till 1st of April online. The course was aimed at healthcare professionals in PGT who wish to learn about genetic counselling.

Professor Kristien Hens talked about the interviews she had conducted for research with couples undergoing preimplantation testing for translocations between 2016 and 2018 at UZ Brussels. She used open-ended interviews and analyzed them in NVIVO.

Recurrent themes were the burden and benefit of the procedure with microarray, the difficulty of defining the good life, and the professional's role. After the presentation, some time was spent reflecting on the need for information about the impact of disability and the need to incorporate experiences of disability infertility practice.

She also presented the B2-Inf project, describing its purpose and goal to close the gap in knowledge between Fertility treatments providers and the broad society.

